

Environmental Data Science Innovation & Impact Lab

The Environmental Data Science Innovation & Impact Lab (ESiIL)

is an NSF-funded data synthesis center that enables a global community of scientists to leverage the wealth of environmental data and emerging analytical tools. ESiIL holds collaboration as a core principle and method for advancing innovative solutions using environmental data science (EDS). ESiIL activities advance the frontier of EDS, a rapidly evolving discipline bridging the computational, biological, environmental, and social sciences.

Priorities Identified by the Environmental Data Science (EDS) Community

Inform ESiIL approach and activities

Top 6 EDS Priorities

Expand access to **training in data skills** and **EDS applications**

77%

Broaden access to **infrastructure** to work with **big data**

57%

Focus EDS on **solving environmental challenges** for society

63%

Create a **supportive and welcoming culture** in the EDS field

54%

Broaden the EDS **workforce**

57%

Improve access to EDS **education resources**, including **AI and Machine Learning**

48%

ESiIL EVENTS & ACTIVITIES

BUILDING A NETWORK AND STRENGTHENING COMMUNITY

The ESIL team includes:

- 32 staff
- 7 postdocs
- 12 current and former advisory board members
- 2 CU Faculty Affiliates

ESIL Network - January 2025

- Social network analyses show enhanced connectivity within an expanding ESIL network
- The most connected individuals are ESIL leadership and current/former board members

Whole network - 261 organizations (yellow), 316 people (blue)

	May 2023	Jan 2025	% Increase
ESIL network members	202	667	+230%
Average degree centrality (average number of connections per person)	2.25	3.4	+ 51%

Node size scaled by degree centrality

41

Partner organizations share data, analytical tools, applications, and cyberinfrastructure (CI); support training, engagement, outreach, conferences, and workshops; advance data sovereignty and Traditional Ecological Knowledge; and foster interdisciplinary approaches to large-scale environmental issues

ESIL communications travel through various community engagement channels

115k Impressions esil.org

580 Newsletter subscribers

1,538 Followers across 5 social media platforms

EVENT HIGHLIGHTS

ESIIL events bring EDS community members together to foster learning and innovation

Hackathons & Codefests

Annual hackathons address topics identified during ESIIL Innovation Summits with hands-on, collaborative, transdisciplinary EDS work

Environmental MosAlc: Using AI to put the Pieces Together Hackathon (Nov. 2023)

- **30 participants** pitched proposals to incorporate AI to handle vast and multi-faceted data to uncover trends, predict future outcomes, and provide real-time insights

Codefests provide training in EDS topics and space for collaborative, data-driven science from ideation through a finished analysis or product

Forest Carbon Codefest (March 2024)

- **28 participants** used cyberinfrastructure and curated datasets to investigate aboveground forest carbon dynamics as they relate to wildfires and other forest disturbances

Working Groups

Self-organized research teams focused on well-defined scientific questions that advance environmental data science

First Cohort

- **7 Working Groups with 111 members**
[Mean = 16 members, range 7-30]
- **75 Unique disciplines represented across working groups**
[Mean = 10.7, Range 4-17]
- **72 Unique Affiliations represented across working groups**
[Mean = 10.3, Range = 6-17]

Innovation Summits

Summit Goals

- Establish collaborations across disciplines, sectors, career stages, and backgrounds
- Explore big data for environmental solutions
- Encourage the co-production of environmental knowledge
- Support accessibility and usability of environmental data, honor data sovereignty, and encourage the responsible use of AI

322 Attendees with 159 unique affiliations

Representing 31 US states and 12 countries: Australia, Brazil, Canada, Denmark, France, Germany, Israel, Kenya, Norway, Panama, Romania, and Sweden

Learning

Resondents ($n = 199$) agreed or strongly agreed that they learned about data science (69%), applicable technology and techniques (61%), Cyber-Infrastructure (58%), and new opportunities to synthesize data in their field (58%)

"I had the opportunity to connect with people outside my discipline, people with expertise I've been looking for but haven't know how to connect with; this is exactly the role I think a synthesis center should be serving in the community."

-2023 ESIIL Summit Participant

SUPPORTING EDS EDUCATION

ESIL increases EDS skills for a data-capable workforce through training modules and an open textbook

ESIL's open education resources reach a global audience via their host learning portal (earthdatascience.org), with

~ **34,000 users**
per month

ESIL Stars

6-month paid internship, online data skills training, career-focused webinars, an open-access textbook with video content, project-based learning

2024 Cohort and Outcomes

Student Snapshot

16 Interns

(first-time participants, undergraduate) and 5 advanced interns (returning, graduate and undergraduate)

Field of study

- 60% Environmental Science/Studies, Conservation Biology
- 20% Computer Science, GIS, Information Technology
- 13% Geoscience, Earth Science
- 7% Indian Law

Student-focused program goals

- Encourage persistence in STEM through career development
- Build applied Earth and EDS skills
- Provide mentorship & community support

Outcomes

100% agreed/strongly agreed that they could see themselves in an EDS career after completing the Stars program ($n = 6$)

TEACHER Snapshot

7 Instructors

Instructors' years of teaching at a college or university level ($n = 6$) varied

- 1 had 0-1 years
- 2 had 2-5 years
- 1 had 6-10 years
- 2 had >10 years

Instructor-focused program goals

- Grow teaching capacity
- Develop curriculum capacity
- Make EDS universally accessible through open education

Outcomes

- 100% ($n = 4$) agreed/strongly agreed that they
- Are confident that they can teach EDS effectively
 - Know where to seek answers to questions they have about teaching EDS
 - Are comfortable answering student questions about EDS effectively
 - Know what to do to increase student interest in EDS

Data Short Course

Introducing educators and leaders to EDS

education tools through a series of 4 courses, 4 weeks each, available as both live online workshops and recorded materials for self-paced learning, ongoing open community forum

38 Participants

 in the first of four courses held in Spring 2024

Affiliation ($n = 24$)

- 63% Higher Education
- 13% Federal Agencies
- 8% Private Organizations
- 4% Non-profit Research Organizations
- 4% Other Non-profit Organizations

Curriculum Focus

- Learn how to incorporate GitHub and Python into curriculum or existing research model

Outcomes

- 100% of respondents ($n = 9$) agreed (44%) or strongly agreed (56%) that after completing the Data Short Course, they felt
- Comfortable with the tools and techniques used to teach EDS
 - Confident in their ability to teach EDS

SUPPORTING OPEN SCIENCE AND DEMOCRATIZED ACCESS

ESILL supports open cyberinfrastructure, scientific collaboration, and community-developed tools, datasets, and reproducible workflows to bridge multiple data types and platforms

GitHub	ESILL-funded (e.g., Working Groups, Postdocs, templates, events/trainings)	Community-created (e.g., by training attendees)
159 Repositories of project files	38	121

USE metrics

2,495 Page Views
of sites hosting repository content

1,253 Clones Made
of repositories for users to work on and sync back to the main repository

2,229 Contributions
reflecting actions taken by users

42 Stars Given
to bookmark or praise a repository

21 Docker Containers allowing applications (code and dependencies) to run across computing environments

- **1,486 Pulls** indicating times when users integrated changes from the public version to their local copies

323 ESILL Community Members were trained to use CyVerse to support their work with large datasets and complex analyses

- 3.6 Million compute hours by ESILL users
- 370 GB of Data stored for active users
- 500 TB of data from Archibald spatial camera and microphone network

70 Recorded EDS Trainings with 15K Views

Publication Highlights

Jennings et al. (2025). Governance of Indigenous data in open earth systems science. *Nature Communications*.

Balch et al. (2024). The fastest growing and most destructive fires in the U.S. (2001-2020). *Science*.

Almeida et al. (2024). Remote sensing approaches to monitor tropical forest restoration: Current options and beyond. *Journal of Applied Ecology*.

Armstrong McKay et al. (2023). Global Tipping Points: 1.3 Tipping points in the biosphere. *The Global Tipping Points*.

Mahood et al. (2023). Ten simple rules for working with high resolution remote sensing data. *Peer Community Journal*.

Iglesias et al. (2022). Fires that Matter: Reconceptualizing fire risk to include feedbacks between humans and the natural environment. *Science Advances*.

SCIENCE PRODUCTS AND OUTPUTS

Members of the EDS community leverage ESILL resources and knowledge to conduct impactful, cutting-edge science

13 Publishing outlets

7 Post-docs

10 Average number of co-authors

25 Publications

18 Conference posters and presentations

Key words from publications

SECURING SYNERGISTIC FUNDING

\$5,765,000+ awarded to CU Boulder's Earth Lab across **23 Grants** with an additional \$330,000+ in ESILL supplements

	Unique Agencies & Sponsors	Total Awarded
Federal	5	\$2,808,225
Industry	5	\$2,584,302
University of Colorado	1	\$373,111

INCORPORATING EVALUATION THROUGHOUT ESIL'S JOURNEY

Collaborative evaluation activities involving ESIL leadership, subteams, and advisory board members contribute to the iterative development and improvement of the synthesis center, the ESIL community, and all ESIL activities

- At ESIL's inception, the evaluation and leadership teams collaborated to define the overarching goals of the center and identify activities and measurable outcomes aligned with each goal
- The evaluation team continuously collaborates with ESIL subteams to develop reflective evaluation approaches that help improve events, trainings, educational programs, and research collaborations
- Each year, evaluators, leadership, and advisory board members reflect on how ESIL is functioning, its progression toward its goals, and how well the team communicates and works collaboratively together

Event Satisfaction

Efforts toward high quality events included providing facilitator training and bringing in professional facilitators. The majority of survey respondents across events were moderately or very satisfied with the event overall

Satisfaction Across Events

Evaluation Products

ESIL received **5 OUT OF 5 STARS** from the external advisory board for its accomplishments

Learn more: esil.org

This work is funded by the National Science Foundation (NSF Award Number DBI-2153040).

